

University of Salento

CoARA
Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

Action Plan
(2025-2028)

Approved by the Academic Senate
25th June 2025

The Community

- The University of Salento is a multidisciplinary community comprising students, faculty, and administrative staff, committed to the free promotion of research and teaching as tools for human development, the affirmation of pluralism, and the pursuit of equal social dignity. This is done with complete independence from any ideological, political, religious, or economic orientation.
- The University of Salento ensures equal opportunities and dignity for all the members of its community, promoting merit and valuing excellence. It supports both basic and applied research, adhering to the principle of evaluation.
- This vision is in line with the principles and commitments outlined in the *Agreement on the Reform of Research Assessment (ARRA)*, signed by the University of Salento in 2022, as well as with the general principles and requirements of the '*European Charter for Researchers*'.

Core principles and values

- The University of Salento, respecting competence and merit, recognizes and implements the principles of equal opportunity, inclusion, and gender equality. Within its community, no one can be discriminated in any way due to his/her choices in research.
- The University promotes the principle of open access to scientific literature, in compliance with laws concerning intellectual property, confidentiality, and the protection and enhancement of cultural heritage.
- The University pursues sustainability in its environmental, social, economic, and cultural dimensions, recognizing its proactive role in the transition to sustainable development, for which it guarantees implementation within its areas of responsibility.

Research strategy and challenges

The University of Salento considers research as its core activity aimed at producing knowledge to advance humanity, and recognizes it as the foundation for both teaching and societal impact. In this regard, the University of Salento intends to adhere to the CoARA reform while committing to carrying out the following actions:

- Train researchers to contribute to knowledge production in public and private sectors.
- Recruit researchers to enrich the University's research potential.
- Establish laboratories and supportive work environments.
- Expand scientific collaborations with other institutions through research networks.
- Support competitive projects to secure research funding.
- Promote research valorization for technology transfer and university spin-offs.
- Monitor research assessment to enhance performance.

Operational and resource management

- The University of Salento makes use of external funding from public and private bodies, while maintaining full autonomy in the planning and development of its community.
- In allocating financial and personnel resources to each Department, the University takes into consideration the results achieved in teaching and research by the members of the Department, using criteria that are not the mere result of quantitative indicators, but are mainly based on qualitative evaluation principles and take into account the growth opportunities of the entire community and the needs of the stakeholders and of the territory.

Quality evaluation and promotion system

- The University of Salento adopts an evaluation and promotion system that includes self-evaluation and external evaluation procedures suitable for ensuring the continuous improvement of the research activities carried out, also through surveys conducted among the entire community.
- The results are used for the allocation of resources and for the activation of reward mechanisms that take into account the complex of activities.
- The system for evaluating and promoting the quality of the University includes the Evaluation Board (“*Nucleo di Valutazione*”) and the Quality Committee (“*Presidio di Qualità*”), which propose guidelines to the University’s governing bodies with the goal of pursuing the quality and effectiveness of all scientific activities and monitoring and analysing the results achieved by the University.

Action Plan and CoARA commitments (1-3)

1. Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

- The University of Salento aims at ensuring that all diverse contributions and achievements are recognized and valued adequately, taking into account scientific aspects together with teaching duties, institutional commitments and “third mission” activities.

2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

- A quality-based approach is applied for internal funding distribution, with a conscious use of widely recognized quantitative indicators.

3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication- based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index

- In compliance with the CoARA reform, the University will limit the use of exclusively bibliometric methods in recruitment and evaluation procedures, promoting the adoption of additional qualitative and quantitative parameters, generally accepted by the scientific community.

Action Plan and CoARA commitments (4-5)

4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organizations in research assessment

- The University of Salento disregards any possibility to consider the use of national or international rankings to allocate resources or to determine the career progression of its researchers.

5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organizational changes committed to

- The University will appoint and establish a dedicated team, whose goal will be to implement all the commitments foreseen in the present Action Plan (and in its future more detailed versions); the team will ensure an adequate representation of all the Departments and will monitor the obtained actions and results.

Action Plan and CoARA commitments (6-7)

6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes

- Italian research institutions are periodically evaluated by an external authority (ANVUR, 'National Agency for the Evaluation of Universities and Research Institutes') which is responsible for the evaluation of Research quality (VQR). The University of Salento is open to contribute to the discussion on the revision of VQR criteria in compliance with CoARA principles (e.g. through the actions carried out in CRUI, the 'Conference of Italian University Rectors').

7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

- The University of Salento will organize and/or host conferences and workshops based on the principles and practices of Open Science. All progress made in implementing the Action Plan will be communicated to the university community, using the feedback received for any future revisions.

Action Plan and CoARA commitments (8-10)

8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

- The University of Salento will actively participate in the Working Groups with other Italian Universities of the CoARA - National Chapter.

9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments

- A detailed document will be published on www.unisalento.it reporting the changes to the criteria for allocating research funds and the effects of the CoARA commitments on research evaluation policies and practices.

10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

- The University of Salento is committed to evaluating the adherence of its scientific production to the principles of Open Science and to carrying out continuous monitoring as a basis for evaluating the policies implemented.

Action Plan implementation phases

- Mid-term plans (from mid-2025 to mid-2026)
 - Establish a dedicated team with representative staff from all Departments.
 - Produce a more detailed Action Plan.
 - Start the implementation of the Action Plan.
 - Raise awareness of the CoARA reform within the academic community.
- Long-term plans (from mid-2026 to 2028)
 - Encourage training activities for young researchers focussing on constant improvement of their research quality.
 - Promote Open Science practices.
 - Discuss and design new evaluation metrics for research assessment in compliance with CoARA principles.
 - Propose criteria to distribute resources within Departments.
 - Monitor the implementation of the Action Plan.
 - Improve the dissemination of the obtained results, both internally and externally.
 - Produce documentation, to be made publicly available for consultation and analysis.